

C. Mutseekwa, R. Martinez

Realizing the Work Potential of People with Disabilities: a Public Opinion Study

KEYWORDS

work potential,
people with
disabilities,
public opinion,
tolerance,
abilities

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Realizing the work potential of people with disabilities is essential for ensuring their right to meaningful employment and social inclusion. Inclusive work practices foster the development of employment opportunities tailored to their needs, promoting innovation and social entrepreneurship.

Understanding public attitudes toward the abilities and potential of people with disabilities is therefore crucial.

Materials and Methods. A survey of 1,000 Almaty residents (553 males, 447 females) was conducted. Statistical methods included Spearman's correlation analysis and principal component analysis with varimax rotation.

Results. Nearly half of respondents (55.4%) believe that people with disabilities can work in regular enterprises, while 33.8% consider employment in specialized enterprises feasible, and 10.8% support home-based work. Among those supporting regular workplaces, most are under 18 years old (36.5%), and among those favoring specialized workplaces, most are under 18 (14.6%). A tolerant attitude toward people with disabilities emerged as a key factor enabling work potential, independent of age, gender, or residence, usually formed through direct interaction.

Conclusion. The majority of respondents view people with disabilities as capable individuals with valuable skills. Those who see them as equals believe they can successfully integrate into standard workplaces or educational institutions. Regular interaction with people with disabilities is associated with positive attitudes and a willingness to provide support.

FOR CITATION

Received: Mar 14, 2025
Accepted: Jun 1, 2025
Published: Sep 1, 2025

Mutseekwa, C., & Martinez, R. (2025). Realizing the Work Potential of People with Disabilities: a Public Opinion Study. *Economic Consultant*, (3), 52–64. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.3.4>

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

Realizing the labor potential of people with disabilities is crucial for their social adaptation, self-esteem, and the development of an inclusive society where everyone has the right to a dignified life and economic participation.

Leveraging this potential expands the workforce, increases productivity, and reduces social costs by lowering unemployment and social isolation among people with disabilities. Inclusive employment practices also foster new forms of work tailored to their needs, promoting innovation and social entrepreneurship.

However, people with disabilities face significant barriers: limited workplace accessibility, biased employer attitudes, lack of adapted working conditions, and insufficient specialized support programs.

Zeyen and Branzei et al. argue that disability often results more from societal barriers than individual biological impairments, with organizations marginalizing individuals and limiting their integration and inclusion [1].

Starzyk and Bauer highlight that employees with disabilities frequently hold lower status and less power due to ableism, emphasizing the role of organizational leaders and policymakers in ensuring these employees have a voice [2].

Grewal et al. identify challenges in employment services for people with disabilities, revealing barriers faced by both providers and employers. Their findings highlight systemic obstacles in employment support, offering insights for policymakers and service providers to better understand the complex experiences of workers with disabilities [3].

Van Ommen et al. note that roughly one-third of cancer survivors face challenges such as forced unemployment and partial or total incapacity following diagnosis and treatment. Returning to paid work is often complicated by perceived employer discrimination and a lack of support, increasing the risk of social isolation. Their study evaluates and confirms the effectiveness and cost-efficiency of the PLACES program, designed to help unemployed or incapacitated cancer survivors re-enter the workforce [4].

Greidanus et al. examine the experiences of unemployed or incapacitated cancer survivors attempting to return to paid work. Most participants (94%) were women, and a majority (56%) successfully re-entered employment. The authors conclude that both internal motivation and external factors drive survivors to return to work, though self-doubt and insufficient support can hinder the process [5].

Regional differences in the labor potential of people with disabilities reflect variations in employment rates, job accessibility, infrastructure, and support programs, as well as regional economic development and availability of specialized enterprises and rehabilitation programs.

Hiesinger et al. provide statistics on employment of people with severe disabilities in Germany, analyzing corporate compliance with workforce quotas and factors associated with higher likelihood of adherence [6].

Buchter observes that despite inclusive workplace legislation in France, many companies struggle to meet disability employment quotas. Some disability rights advocates have become managers responsible for disability inclusion, shaping organizational policy since the late 2000s [7].

Dueñas-Zambrana and Cruz-Morato highlight persistent inequality and labor isolation for people with disabilities in both developing and developed economies, including Spain. They propose social marketing as a tool to advance the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals [8].

Pesor and Pöder study the impact of Estonia's 2016 active labor market reforms which introduced new vocational rehabilitation policies. They show that post-rehabilitation employment lasts on average 2.6 months longer than for those who discontinued the program. While completing the rehabilitation plan positively affects employment outcomes, maintaining employment remains challenging due to the modest size of the effect [9].

Ozel et al. argue that the prevalence of disability in society underscores the need to expand rights and opportunities for people with disabilities, enabling their participation in social and economic life. Analyzing individuals employed in forestry in Turkey's Western Black Sea region between 2018 and 2021, the authors observed increased participation despite reduced income due to fewer working days. To create more inclusive opportunities, people with disabilities can be trained for specialized roles, such as planning and monitoring in forestry [10].

Salamzadeh et al. examine opportunities in Iran to identify entrepreneurial challenges faced by people with disabilities and propose strategies for creating and developing disability-led startups. The authors emphasize the role of government in reforming societal attitudes to enhance the economic activity of people with disabilities [11].

Zhang et al. investigate the impact of subsidies and employment support on policy development for disabled veterans in China. They report that subsidies positively

influence well-being, though this effect diminishes with increasing disability severity. Employment contributes to well-being by enhancing self-identity [12].

Emerging technologies facilitate the labor potential of people with disabilities by creating accessible work environments, employing adaptive devices and software, and enabling online learning and remote work.

Lillywhite et al. note that people with disabilities face challenges in ensuring personal well-being. They suggest that artificial intelligence (AI) technologies can enhance well-being by helping individuals overcome limitations or simplify task performance [13].

Rouse and McBride explore AI-based assistive technologies for people with cognitive impairments through two case studies. They introduce a wearable, human-centered coaching device that functions as both a vocational coach and a counselor, and discuss the potential of autonomous vehicles for people with disabilities and older adults [14].

Gooding examines AI-driven biometric monitoring and automated decision-making systems in the context of disability and mental health. The focus is on “digital phenotyping” or behavioral sensor analytics across diverse settings, including hospitals, social services, homes, correctional facilities, and consumer products. The author underscores the importance of active involvement of people with disabilities in managing these automated profiling systems and shaping the scientific discourse behind them [15].

Poonkuzhali et al. note that providing life skills to individuals with intellectual disabilities requires special attention to enable relative independence, including access to social support. They propose a life-skills program for individuals with mild to moderate intellectual disabilities, implemented via a web-based e-learning tool featuring video collections, 3D animations, and augmented reality within a structured curriculum [16].

Increasing participation of people with disabilities in the workforce depends on creating accessible workplaces, implementing adaptive technologies, developing vocational rehabilitation programs, promoting inclusive employment, and raising public awareness.

Yıldız and Yıldız describe inclusive growth as a form of economic development where wealth and opportunities are equitably distributed, ensuring equal access for all. They analyze the labor market in Turkey, highlighting employment and equality as critical elements of sustainable social well-being. The authors argue that reducing existing inequalities, starting with vulnerable groups, and increasing their labor participation are crucial for fostering inclusive growth and societal welfare [17].

Lee et al. examine changes in self-rated health among individuals with occupational disabilities, identifying latent classes and prognostic factors. They identified four health-trajectory classes: low-declining (21.7%), moderate-growing (15.7%), high-declining (56.1%), and low-stable (6.5%). Multinomial logistic regression revealed that key determinants, such as age, work ability, type of workplace accident, disability severity, cognitive activity, outdoor activity, and social relationships, varied across classes. Strategies to improve self-rated health should be tailored to each latent class [18].

Sharma and Prabhu draw on longitudinal interviews conducted over three years (late 2019 to early 2023) with eight individuals with disabilities, tracing their experiences from initial encounters with disability to education in a leading business school and early workforce participation. They conclude that people with disabilities can enhance workplace self-efficacy and competitiveness without requiring additional support [19].

Kurnianto et al. explore support opportunities through medical, professional, and psychological rehabilitation in return-to-work (RTW) programs in low-income countries. They note that RTW programs benefit companies, and that providing career development services or collaborating with NGOs ensures continued engagement in socially useful activities for employees who cannot return to previous employers [20].

Sydorenko et al. investigate strategies for enhancing business competitiveness by leveraging the labor potential of low-mobility populations, including the largest groups: people with disabilities and working retirees. They develop an econometric model to identify key factors influencing the labor force in this category [21].

Kruse et al. examine how access to assistive technologies affects employment and earnings of people with disabilities. Their data indicate that most functional limitations correlate with lower employment and earnings, especially among those with mobility impairments, and particularly low wages among individuals with cognitive disabilities. Between 2012 and 2021, only about one-tenth of workers with disabilities received any adaptive services, with just 3–4% accessing equipment-based adaptations [22].

Overall, these studies underscore that society and organizations play a critical role in shaping disability by creating barriers to integration. Ableism and discrimination reduce the status and opportunities of employees with disabilities. Systemic challenges exist in employment, and returning to work after serious illnesses, such as cancer, is complicated by discrimination and insufficient support. Research highlights the importance of support programs and motivation in facilitating successful workforce reintegration despite internal doubts and external obstacles.

Various authors emphasize the importance of inclusive growth, equitable distribution of societal opportunities and wealth, and reducing inequalities to increase participation of vulnerable groups in the labor market. Development of rehabilitation programs, enhancement of self-efficacy, and use of assistive technologies contribute to workforce integration and competitiveness of people with disabilities.

Analyzing the realization of labor potential among people with disabilities remains a relevant and scientifically significant topic. Accordingly, examining public perceptions of citizens' abilities and opportunities to fulfill this potential is a key task.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials for the study included articles from reputable journals, such as the *Journal of Business Ethics*, *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, *Journal of Cancer Survivorship*, *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, *AI & Society: Knowledge, Culture and Communication*, among others.

A questionnaire survey of the population was conducted in Almaty, Kazakhstan, from November 12 to 26, 2023, to examine public opinions on citizens' possibilities and abilities to realize their labor potential. A total of 1,000 people participated in the survey, comprising 55.3% men and 44.7% women.

Questionnaire Items

Demographic characteristics of respondents

1. Age:
 - Under 18;
 - 18-45 years;
 - Over 45 years
2. Gender:
 - Male;
 - Female
3. Employment status:
 - Employed;
 - Studying;
 - Not currently working or studying

Perceptions of citizens with disabilities

4. In your opinion, where can people with disabilities work?

- Regular enterprises;
- Specially created enterprises (workplaces);
- Only at home

Statistical methods

Correlation analysis (Spearman) and principal component analysis with varimax rotation were used.

RESULTS

The age distribution of respondents was as follows: 57.7% under 18, 30.7% ranging 18-45, and 11.6% over 45 (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Age and gender distribution of respondents, (%)

The primary objective of the study was to assess the opinions of the middle-aged population, as younger respondents have relatively limited social experience and may not be able to form well-founded opinions on the topic, while respondents over 45 years old have a relatively higher prevalence of disability, which could bias their responses. This approach also addressed the study's methodological goal.

Among respondents under 18 years old, 35.2% were male and 18.5% female. In the 18-45-year-old group, males comprised 14.2% and females 21.0%. Among respondents over 45 years, 4.4% were male and 7.2% female.

Regarding employment, 25.2% of respondents were employed, 74.2% were students, and 0.6% were neither working nor studying (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Respondents' attitude to employment, (%)

The respondents' perception of citizens with disabilities is presented in Fig. 3.

Experience with people with disabilities was reported as follows: 36.2% communicate daily, 38.4% occasionally, and 25.4% have no such experience. Male respondents reported more experience interacting with people with disabilities than females.

Figure 3 Respondents' experience with people with disabilities, (%)

Overall, 70.4% of respondents regard people with disabilities as ordinary individuals (38.2% men, 32.2% women). The remaining responses suggest a generally tolerant rather than indifferent attitude: respondents are reluctant to treat people with

disabilities as societal outcasts, to patronize them excessively, and instead recognize them as full members of society. People perceived as often needing assistance make up 17.9% of respondents (9.4% men, 8.5% women), while 5.3% express pity (2.9% men, 2.4% women). The data indicate that men display a slightly higher degree of sympathy toward people with disabilities (see Fig. 4).

Figure 4 Respondents' answers to the question "What is your attitude to people with disabilities?", (%)

Regarding the ability to work, nearly half of the respondents believe that people with disabilities can be employed at regular enterprises (55.4% of respondents). A smaller proportion, 33.8%, consider employment at specially created enterprises for people with limited health possible, while only 10.8% think that people with disabilities can work from home.

Figure 5 Respondents' answers to the question "In your opinion, where can people with disabilities work?", (%)

Among those who believe that people with disabilities can work in ordinary jobs, the majority are under 18 years old (36.5%). Of the 16.8% of respondents who think people with disabilities can work in specially created workplaces, most are also under 18 (14.6%).

Additionally, a correlation analysis of the sample results (Spearman) was performed, and the results of the factor analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Age	0.254	0.834
Gender	-0.099	0.486
Attitude to employment	-0.257	-0.850
Experience of communication	0.796	0.077
Personal attitude	0.535	0.192
Work	0.759	0.012
Extraction method: Principal component analysis. Rotation method: Varimax with Kaiser normalization.		
Note. Rotation convergent in 5 iterations.		

Factor interpretation:

Factor 1: Tolerant attitude toward people with disabilities

Factor 2: Bipolar factor (the older the respondent, the more engaged in work, and vice versa).

The analysis identified the primary factor: a tolerant attitude toward people with disabilities which appears independent of age, gender, or place of residence. Typically, this attitude is shaped through direct communication and interaction with people with disabilities.

DISCUSSION

The survey demonstrates that people with disabilities can effectively work and study when the right conditions and support are provided. Many already succeed across diverse fields [23; 24], especially where employers adopt inclusive and adaptive strategies. Accessible jobs [25], assistive technologies, and rehabilitation

programs [26] are crucial. Participation in mainstream education is also possible with necessary accommodations, such as accessible facilities and tailored materials.

Inclusive education enhances socialization and skill development, improving employment prospects. With proper support and adaptation, people with disabilities can fully integrate into both professional and educational environments.

CONCLUSION

The survey found that 78.3% of respondents (45.2% men, 33.1% women) view people with disabilities as ordinary individuals, acknowledging their skills, strengths, and abilities. Those who hold this view generally believe that people with disabilities can work in regular enterprises or study in educational institutions. Daily interaction with people with disabilities is associated with friendliness and a willingness to provide support.

REFERENCES

1. Zeyen, A., Branzei, O. (2023). Disabled at Work: Body-Centric Cycles of Meaning-Making. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 185, 767–810. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-023-05344-w>
2. Starzyk, A., Bauer, J. F. (2025). Three Dilemmas of Disabled Employee Voice. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-025-05964-4>
3. Grewal, E., Durocher, E., Premji, S. et al. (2025). Exploring Intersections of Race and Disability in the Context of Canadian Employment Support Systems Through the Experiences of Job Seekers/Workers, Employers, and Service Providers. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-025-10291-6>
4. van Ommen, F., Duijts, S. F. A., Coenen, P. et al. (2024). Protocol of a randomized controlled trial on the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of the PLACES intervention: a supported employment intervention aimed at enhancing work participation of unemployed and/or work-disabled cancer survivors. *Trials* 25, 603. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-024-08441-x>
5. Greidanus, M. A., van Ommen, F., & de Boer, A. G. E. M. et al. (2024). Experiences of unemployed and/or work-disabled cancer survivors who have pursued to return to paid employment: a focus group study. *Journal of Cancer Survivorship*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11764-024-01657-5>
6. Hiesinger, K., Pohlan, L., & Vetter, F. (2025). The employment statistics of severely disabled people: description and research potential. *Journal for Labour Market Research*, 59, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12651-025-00395-0>
7. Buchter, L. (2025). "We are Our Own Best Advocates": When Disability Rights Activists Constructed Legal Compliance to Address Ableism in France. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-025-05959-1>
8. Dueñas-Zambrana, C., & Cruz-Morato, M. A. (2023). Corporate Social Marketing and the Labor Inclusion of People with Disabilities. A Case Study of Ilunion Hotels. In: Galan-Ladero, M. M., Alves, H. M. (eds) *Social Marketing and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)*. Springer Business Cases. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27377-3_6

9. Pesor, R., & Pöder, K. (2024). Evaluation of Active Labor Market Policy Reform: Employment Outcomes of Vocational Rehabilitation Services. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 34, 116–127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-023-10102-w>
10. Ozel, H. B., Sevik, H., & Cetin, M. et al. (2024). Impact of employment policies on disabled individuals in silvicultural activities. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-024-05036-z>
11. Salamzadeh, A., Dana, LP., Mortazavi, S., & Hadizadeh, M. (2022). Exploring the Entrepreneurial Challenges of Disabled Entrepreneurs in a Developing Country. In: Dana, LP., Khachlouf, N., Maâlaoui, A., Ratten, V. (eds) *Disadvantaged Minorities in Business. Contributions to Management Science*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97079-6_5
12. Zhang, Q., Wang, Y., & Lin, Y. et al. (2024). From Handouts to Empowerment: Impacts of Policy Subsidies and Employment Support on the Well-Being of Disabled Veterans. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 25, 110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-024-00809-9>
13. Lillywhite, A., Wolbring, G. (2024). Coverage of well-being within artificial intelligence, machine learning and robotics academic literature: the case of disabled people. *AI & SOCIETY*, 39, 2537–2555. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01735-9>
14. Rouse, W. B., & McBride, D. K. (2023). Assistive Technologies for Disabled and Older Adults. In: Madni, A. M., Augustine, N., Sievers, M. (eds) *Handbook of Model-Based Systems Engineering*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93582-5_65
15. Gooding, P. (2024). Power, Personhood, and Data-Driven Technologies in the Lives of Disabled People: The Rise of Profiling Technologies in Mental Health Settings. In: Rioux, M. H., Buettgen, A., Zubrow, E., Viera, J. (eds) *Handbook of Disability*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6056-7_87
16. Poonkuzhali, S., Vijay, P., Shanthi, D. S., & Archana, J. S. (2024). Development and Pilot Testing of a Web-Based E-Learning Tool for Imparting Livelihood Skills of Intellectually Disabled Person. In: Senjyu, T., So-In, C., Joshi, A. (eds) *Smart Trends in Computing and Communications. SmartCom 2024 2024. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 945*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-1320-2_35
17. Yildiz, E., & Yildiz, N. (2025). Analysis of the Labor Market in Turkey with a Focus on Inclusive Growth. In: Çaliyurt, K. T. (eds) *New Approaches to CSR, Sustainability and Accountability, Volume VI. Accounting, Finance, Sustainability, Governance & Fraud: Theory and Application*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-96-5937-1_10
18. Lee, S., Park, H. N., & Yoon, J. Y. (2024). Trajectories of Self-Rated Health Among Industrially Disabled Individuals: A Latent Class Growth Analysis. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 34, 630–643. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-023-10151-1>
19. Sharma, D., & Prabhu, G. N. (2025). Navigating Competency in an Ableist World: The Lived Experiences of Disabled Individuals in Education and the Workplace. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-025-05958-2>
20. Kurnianto, A. A., Khatatbeh, H., & Prémusz, V. et al. (2023). Managing disabled workers due to occupational accidents in Indonesia: a case study on return to work program. *BMC Public Health*, 23, 943. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15930-2>
21. Sydorenko, O. et al. (2024). Determining the Composition of the Working-Age Population in the Low-Mobility Group in Ukraine. In: El Khoury, R. (eds) *Anticipating Future Business Trends: Navigating Artificial Intelligence Innovations. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control, vol 536*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-63402-4_47
22. Kruse, D., Schur, L., & Johnson-Marcus, HA. et al. (2024). Assistive Technology's Potential to Improve Employment of People with Disabilities. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 34, 299–315. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-023-10164-w>

23. Rosenbaum, S. A. (2023). A Rationale and Roadmap for Paralegal Clinics: Advocating for Disabled Children and Youth. In: *Bajpai, A., Tushaus, D. W., Prasad, M. R. K. (eds) Human Rights and Legal Services for Children and Youth*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-5551-0_5
24. Reinarts, N., & Melo, V. (2023). ADA to Ph.D.? The Americans with disabilities act and post-secondary educational attainment. *Public Choice*, 197, 421–432. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11127-023-01075-8>
25. Brooks, J. D., & von Schrader, S. (2023). An Accommodation for Whom? Has the COVID-19 Pandemic Changed the Landscape of Flexible and Remote Work for Workers with Disabilities? *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-023-09472-3>
26. Nordin, N., Nordin, N., Nordin, N. I. A., Nordin, N. F., & Ewan, E. E. (2022). The Needs Analysis for Development of Smart 3-wheel Bike for Disabled Entrepreneurs. In: *Alareeni, B., Hamdan, A. (eds) Financial Technology (FinTech), Entrepreneurship, and Business Development. ICBT 2021. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 486*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-08087-6_59
27. Rohman, A., & Vo, DT. (2025). "To us, it is still foreign": AI and the disabled in the Global South. *AI & SOCIETY*, 40, 2259–2271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-024-02149-x>
28. Simonovits, B., Kurdi, B. & Simonovits, G. (2023). Disabled and Romani passengers face similar levels of discrimination but different levels of open hostility in the sharing economy. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 10605. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-37263-1>
29. Kulkarni, M. (2024). Narrating a Prototypical Disabled Employee. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 189, 781–796. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05266-z>
30. Baeken, A., Forrier, A. & De Cuyper, N. (2025). Is Work Still a Right if it has Become a Norm? Disability Inclusion in Labor Market Policy Discourse. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-025-05962-6>
31. Rymenans, I., Vanovenberghe, C., & Du Bois, M. et al. (2024). Process Evaluation of a Motivational Interviewing Intervention in a Social Security Setting: A Qualitative Study among Work-Disabled Patients. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 34, 141–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-023-10108-4>

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Christopher Mutseekwa	PhD, Department of Curriculum and Educational Management Studies, Faculty of Science Education. Bindura University of Science Education (Zimbabwe, Bindura). E-mail: chrismutseekwa@gmail.com . Scopus Author ID: 57880894800	Writing - Original Draft, Visualization
Ramiro Martinez	Researcher. Institute of Economic Research. National Autonomous University of Mexico (Mexico, Mexico City). E-mail: ramirobass2017@gmail.com	Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

Copyright: © Christopher Mutseekwa, Ramiro Martinez, 2025

Editor: Alexandru Trifu. Gheorghe Zane University (Romania)